

KEY INDICATORS

The organic sector holds a prominent position within Austria's agricultural industry. Austria is the only EU country to already exceed the EU target of 25% (on average) of agricultural land under organic management, reaching almost 700 kha (27.2%) in 2024. This represents a 52% growth compared with 2001. Austria is also among the top countries regarding organic market share reaching a retail sales value of almost 2,887.9 million euros or 11.4% of the total national food market in 2024, up more than 1000% compared with 2001. These developments built on organic policy support already since 1992, including the environmental programme ÖPUL, as well as high consumer demand for organic products and increased producer prices since 2017. Organic retail sales rely on the broad availability of organic products in highly concentrated retail chains.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)	459,326 ha (15.7%)	698,590 ha (27.2%)
Area Growth from 2001 to 2024	52.1%	

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)	78,072 ha (5.9%)	293,675 ha (22.2%)
Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)	2,284 ha (2.8%)	15,419 ha (22.7%)
Grassland* (Share of Total)	326,239 ha (22.4%)	389,496 ha (31%)
Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)	N/D	239 † (5.3%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)	18,290 (11.6%)	25,342 (22.9%)
Aquaculture Producers	N/D	40
Processors	573	2,328
Importers	30	86

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)	225 M €	2,887.9 M€ (11.4%)
Per Capita Consumption	28.1 €	292 €
Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024	1,1834%	
Imports	N/D	41,061 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN AUSTRIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on BMLRT, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN AUSTRIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on AMA Marketing and further sources

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Austrian CAP strategic plan provides for modest increases in organic area supported and expenditure, with more environmental requirements being added to the organic support scheme, while payment rates for arable and horticulture are reduced. The 23% of UAA planned to be supported in 2027 contrasts with the 27.5% certified organic in 2022, and the 35% targeted for 2030. Additional costs during conversion are not compensated.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	515 kha	610 kha (+18%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	19.4%	23% (+18%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	80.6%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	121 M€	154 M€ (+27%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	234 €	252 € (+7%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	753 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	500 M€	26.3%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	2,362 M€	8.7%
Total CAP Expenditure	8,650 M€	

*Including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	70-225	230-550	450	500-700	700
	2024	P2	76-272	235-559	451	540-756	756
Change from 2023 to 2024			9%-21%	2%	0%	8%	8%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	70-225	230-550	450	500-700	700
	2024	P2	76-272	235-559	451	540-756	756
Change from 2023 to 2024			9%-21%	2%	0%	8%	8%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2024		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Austria has had a series of organic action plans starting in 2001. The latest (the sixth) Austrian national OAP contains more market-related actions than previously, with a corresponding emphasis on improving market, financial and statistical information, and strengthening promotion of organic farming benefits to consumers.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2015-22	20% of UAA by 2016, more by 2020	100% of organic products sold as organic by 2022
Current Action Plan	2023-30	30% of UAA by 2027, 35% by 2030	22% of canteen food by 2023, 55% by 2030*

*Source: Austrian Action Plan for Sustainable Public Procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2015 - 2022)

RDP area and investment (+5%) support

Group actions, promotion of AMA logo

Public information, publications
 Support for advice, training, research
 Provision of financial data on organic farming

PRODUCTION

MARKETS

INFORMATION

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

CSP area and investment (+5%) support

Supply chain development, increased focus on public procurement, tourism, gastronomy, exports, logos

Consumer promotion campaign with focus on environmental and animal welfare benefits; increase range of advisory services, maintain training and research programmes; improve availability of financial, market, statistical data

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Austria is just over 5%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids and consumer information. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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Design
 CONSULAI

Publication year
 2026

FiBL

THÜNEN

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